

LABORATORY MODEL OF A MAGNETIC LEVITATION SYSTEM

Yassen Gorbounov¹, Petar Peychinov²

¹University of Mining and Geology "St. Ivan Rilski", 1700 Sofia; y.gorbounov@mgu.bg

²University of Mining and Geology "St. Ivan Rilski", 1700 Sofia; petar.peychinov@abv.bg

ABSTRACT. The magnetic levitation consists of balancing the forces of attraction and repulsion of a ferromagnetic object located in a foreign magnetic field in such a way as to keep a desired distance between the object and the magnet. This technology is receiving increasing attention because it helps to eliminate the frictional losses due to the lack of mechanical contact. This makes it possible to reduce the wear of critical machine parts and achieve high speeds with increased positioning accuracy. Advanced applications include the high-speed Maglev trains, magnetic bearings and suspension, electromagnetic cranes, high-accuracy positioning of wafers in photolithography in the manufacturing of integrated circuits, and other high-precision contactless positioning devices. Positive results are also observed in applications from the mining and processing industry in the extraction and processing of raw materials, which makes the topic relevant. The paper presents a laboratory model of a single degree of freedom electromagnet-based system intended to aid the studying of the effect of magnetic levitation. The possibilities for the implementation of different positional feedback types are discussed together with the power circuit that drives the electromagnet. A mathematical model and implementation of a fully digital algorithm that uses the PID control law are presented. Experiments are conducted that could aid in building a sensorless control system. The elaborated laboratory model allows for easy upgrade and can be used in disciplines in the field of measurement, control, and automation as a whole.

Keywords: Magnetic Levitation, Pulse Width Modulation, Programmable Logic Device, Processing of Raw Materials

Introduction

The levitation is a way of lifting and suspending an object in the air without physical support and contact with the ground or other objects. To overcome the gravitational force of attraction, it is necessary to create a counteracting force that is large enough to lift the object. Next, a control algorithm is needed to achieve a stable equilibrium that keeps the object at the desired distance. Various types of creating levitation exist based on the nature of the occurrence of the counteracting force such as electrostatic levitation, aerodynamic levitation, acoustic, optical, and magnetic levitation to name a few. What they have in common is the lack of physical contact between the object and its environment and therefore the lack of friction and wearing. In addition they eliminate lubricants that can be a source of contamination. All of the above is of extreme benefit for linearly or rotational moving devices that pave the way for the myriad applications of the levitation (Yaghoubi, 2013) such as the Maglev train with either servo-stabilised electromagnetic suspension (EMS) or electrodynamic suspension (EDS) (Vuchic, 2002; Hyung et al., 2006), wind turbines (Manoj, 2019), frictionless magnetic bearings (Hiroyuki, 2000, Qiao, 2020), magnetic separation of raw materials (Alexandrov, 2013; Peng, 2018), aerospace engineering like the launch ring (McNab, 2003; Hull, 2007), medical applications like the blood pump (Wang, 2016), etc. Research is also being done to use the magnetic levitation technology for contactless, high-precision positioning of wafers in photolithography (Lahdo, 2016).

In the field of education many companies exist such as Quanser (Quanser, 2019), Inteco (Inteco, 2005), Feedback Instruments (Feedback Instruments, 2019) and others that offer lab-ready kits but they are expensive and are often associated with the use of commercial software such as Matlab in combination with proprietary hardware. Therefore, this paper presents a laboratory model of a Magnetic Levitation System (MLS) built at the University of Mining and Geology „St. Ivan Rilski“. It represents a single degree of freedom MLS that allows for levitating a hollow metallic ball vertically up and down. The platform can be easily extended to conduct various

experiments and do research in the field of magnetic levitation and control systems.

Essence of the problem

The basic working principle of the laboratory model is depicted in Fig. 1. It helps to reveal the control goal of the system which consists of supporting a hollow steel ball in the air at a desired distance apart from an electromagnet.

Fig. 1. Working principle of the magnetic levitation plant

The system consists of a controller (CTRL) which applies pulse width modulated signal (PWM) to the power stage (PWR) to control the current I_c through the coil of the electromagnet. This current can be calculated by measuring the voltage drop V_s across the current sense resistor R_s . In the figure the coil is presented with its active resistance R_c and its inductance L_c . The electromagnet generates an electromagnetic force F_c which counteracts the force of gravity F_g . The hollow steel sphere is placed along the vertical axis of the electromagnet at some distance (air gap) δ apart from it. The size of the air gap is measured with the aid of the sensor S and is fed back to the controller which algorithm calculates and adjusts the new PWM value.

The mathematical description can be done by writing the equations for the voltage and the mechanical part of the circuit. It should be noted that the electrical subsystem is much faster

than the mechanical subsystem. The coil current can be computed using the relationship (1):

$$V_s(t) = R_s \cdot i_s(t) \quad (1)$$

Using the Kirchoff's law the following first-order equation can be derived (2):

$$V_c(t) = (R_c + R_s) \cdot i_c(t) + L_c \frac{di_c(t)}{dt} \quad (2)$$

The force that is experienced by the ferromagnetic sphere is given by the fundamental principle of dynamics – the second Newton's law of motion (3):

$$F_R = F_g - F_c = m \cdot g - k \cdot \left(\frac{i_c(t)}{\delta} \right)^2 \quad (3)$$

Where F_R is the resultant force, m is the ball mass, g is the gravity force and k is the magnetic force constant for the electromagnet-ball pair. In order for the ball to levitate in the air it is necessary to reach the condition of equilibrium (4):

$$F_g = F_c \rightarrow m \cdot g = k \cdot \left(\frac{i_c(t)}{\delta} \right)^2 \quad (4)$$

Solving for the current gives (5) which allows to obtain the current value as a function of the air gap δ .

$$i_c(t) = \sqrt{\frac{m \cdot g}{k}} \cdot \delta^2 \quad (5)$$

The influence of the air gap over the force produced by the electromagnet F_c can be plotted by solving (6).

$$F_c = (n \cdot i_c(t))^2 \cdot k \cdot \frac{s}{\delta^2} \quad (6)$$

In this equation n is the number of turns in the coil and s is the area. The 3D plot for F_c as a function of the current and the air gap is shown in Fig. 2.

Fig. 2. Three-dimensional plot for $F_c(I, \delta)$

As can be seen, the function is highly nonlinear. Given these data it becomes obvious that the distance can be controlled over a narrow range of about 0 to 2 cm depending on the properties of the ferromagnetic object. The near to zero distance is of no practical interest since the precision and dynamics of the control at very small air gaps are limited by the saturation conditions.

Feedback sensor types

In order to levitate the ferromagnetic object in the space a good estimation of the size of the air gap is needed. Many types of distance feedback techniques exist that are appropriate for this MLS laboratory model. They can be classified as passive or active, by the nature of the signal they emit (if any) or by their working principle. Some of the most popular sensors are discussed briefly below.

Photoelectric sensors

The family of the photoelectric sensors includes any pair of light-emitting and photodetector devices but the infrared (IR) and laser-based sensors are most common because they are less sensitive to the daylight spectrum. Two effects can be used here – the reflection from the target or the beam intersection. The most common case is to mount an optocouple split between both the vertical columns of the MLS frame. This way the levitating object intersects the light beam by either reducing the light intensity falling on the receiver or interrupting one or more light beams in the case where the sensor is in the form of an array. The other possibility is to use a distance measurement reflective isotropic position sensitive device (PSD) like the Sharp GP2D12 or a laser ranging sensor such as the ST VL53L0X. The first one is a non-monotonic transducer which means that its static characteristics have no inversion so that it is not applicable for small distances because the readings may be ambiguous. The second one employs the time-of-flight (ToF) principle but it is pricey and poses higher requirements for mounting precision. Both the Sharp and the ST sensors are sensitive to the colour of the object and its diffusing properties.

Acoustic sensors

The acoustic sensors are usually ultrasonic devices like the HC-SR04 transducer. They are active sensors that emit high frequency sound wave to the object and calculate the time it takes for the reflected sound wave to get back to the receiver. This principle is called the time-of-flight (ToF) and is given in (7):

$$d = \frac{t \cdot v}{2} \quad (7)$$

Where d is the distance to the object, t is the time for the wave to get to and back from the object and v is the speed of sound in the medium (the air) which is slightly dependent on the temperature. This sensor can be mounted under the object but it does not cope well with its spherical shape – the ball, and is mostly suitable for higher distance ranges as its measurement accuracy is relatively low.

Capacitive sensors

The capacitive sensors can detect both ferromagnetic and non-ferromagnetic targets. Their principle of operation is based on the use of two conduction plates at different potentials with little capacitance between them, that are linked to an oscillator, and a frequency counter. The air acts as an insulator and the object alters the capacitance thus changing the oscillator frequency. The capacitive sensors are moisture sensitive devices so the room conditions may impede their readings. They can be mounted under the ferromagnetic ball but their linearity and sensitivity is not good enough for the purpose of the current MLS.

Magnetosensitive sensors

There exist two major categories of magnetosensitive devices which are based on two galvanomagnetic effects – the Gaussian effect and the Hall effect.

The first category covers the magnetoresistive sensors where the active resistance R depends on the induction B of the magnetic field. This category in turn includes the anisotropic magnetoresistive sensors (AMR) and the giant magnetoresistive sensors (GMR) which are commercially available. The GMR effect was discovered relatively soon (1988) and its discovery was awarded the 2007 Nobel prize in physics.

The second category covers the Hall effect sensors. The essence of the Hall effect is that if a current carrying conductor is placed in a magnetic field with magnetic induction, perpendicular to the current, then an electric field emerges in that conductor in a direction which is perpendicular to both the current and the induction. This field creates a transverse potential difference called the Hall voltage. The proposed MLS employs the continuous-time linear Hall effect sensor A1302 by Allegro Microsystems. Its low price, small size, high sensitivity of 1,3 mV/G and high linearity emphasises its advantages over other sensors. The generalised dimensionless transfer characteristics of this type of sensors are depicted in Fig. 3 (Pepka, 2013).

Fig. 3. Transfer characteristics of A1302 throughout the range of sensed magnet flux, courtesy of Allegro (Pepka, 2013)

It can be seen in the figure that the characteristic is quite linear and there are two saturation areas which limit the minimum and maximum voltage. Since the hollow ferromagnetic ball acts as a ferromagnetic concentrator of the magnetic flux the output voltage is in proportion with the size of the air gap which is linearised by the integrated circuit (IC).

The construction of the proposed laboratory model allows for any type of feedback sensor to be easily mounted onto the frame.

Power stage circuit

Although a simplified solution like a discrete MOSFET transistor is appropriate here, a dedicated fully integrated H-bridge driver is used to power the electromagnet. This is the ST VN5019 based Arduino shield from Pololu (2019). The block diagram of the power stage is shown in Fig. 4.

Fig. 4. Block diagram of the VN5019

The electromagnet coil is connected between the OUT_A and OUT_B leads of the integrated circuit. The n-type MOSFET transistors HS_A, LS_A, HS_B and LS_B form a full bridge that is capable of four-quadrant operation and can provide current of up to 30A. The VN5019 IC is chosen because it supports protective functions such as undervoltage, overvoltage and thermal shutdown, cross-conduction protection and current limitation which are invaluable for the experimental MLS platform. Additional advantage is the provided current sense capability which allows for measuring the current through the coil.

Control algorithm

Because the electromagnetic levitation system described in this paper is intended to be used mainly for teaching, a universal proportional-integral-derivative (PID) control algorithm is implemented. It is a closed-loop feedback system subjected to the three-component control law (8):

$$u(t) = k_P \cdot e(t) + k_I \cdot \int_0^t e(\tau) d\tau + k_D \cdot \frac{e(t)}{dt} \tag{8}$$

Where $u(t)$ is the control signal, $e(t)$ is the error derived by subtracting the real position from the setpoint, and k_P , k_I , k_D are the tuning parameters for the corresponding gains.

The proportional (P) term alters the control variable proportional to the loop error and it takes effect instantly. The P term is not able to minimize the loop error to zero. The integral (I) term alters the control variable proportional to the loop error and its course over time. It does not work instantly, but it is able to fully minimize the loop error. The derivative (D) term has to do with how fast the error changes. By manipulating each of the k_P , k_I , and k_D parameters the responsiveness and the stability of the control loop can be examined.

The general block diagram of the implemented closed-loop MLS system is shown in Fig. 5. The plant is directly driven by the power amplifier (Power Shield) which input is taken from the PWM output stage of the Arduino controller. The plant is covered by a negative feedback in a closed-loop control system. Its behaviour is being measured by the Hall effect sensor and the result is read by the analogue-to-digital (ADC) converter of the controller. The assignment (setpoint) and the control gains are set by the personal computer which connects to the controller via serial (USB) link.

Fig. 5. Block diagram of the implemented closed-loop MLS

For the practical implementation of the PID control algorithm an open source library is used (Sirgado, 2019). The portion of the code that implements the PID calculations is given in Table 1.

The code is self-explanatory and follows directly the PID control law (8). All the values are of floating point type and are easily accessible via terminal software. The calibration of the MLS is left to the student although the system proves to be stable with $k_i=0,7$, $k_p=5,0$, $k_i=4,3$, and $k_D=0,4$ for a sphere of 70 mm of diameter, 130 g. Experiments were conducted with a larger sphere (100 mm, 250 g) where the stability is reached with $k_i=0,7$, $k_p=30,2$, $k_i=6,3$, and $k_D=0,5$.

Table 1. Arduino code snippet for the PID calculations

```
// Hall Sensor Read (Magnetic Field Intensity);
anaVal = analogRead(anaPin);
// PID calculations
measured_value = anaVal;
error = setpoint - measured_value;
integral = integral + error * dt;
derivative = (error - previous_error) / dt;
output = (-Kp * error) + (-Ki * integral) + (-Kd * derivative);
previous_error = error;
// Final value setup
digVal += output;
```

Experimental work

The general overview of the elaborated physical experimental platform is shown in Fig. 6.

Fig. 6. General overview of the laboratory model of the MLS: the MLS frame and the controller (a), and the air gap of 6 mm (b)

In Fig. 6(a) the MLS frame is shown levitating a hollow ferromagnetic ball with a diameter of 100 mm, 250 g. The controller box which includes the Arduino microcontroller and the Pololu power shield is visible at the bottom of the figure. In Fig. 6(b) the air gap which is about 6 mm in size is shown on an enlarged scale.

Additional measurements are performed to determine the flux linkage as a function of the current through the winding

and the size of the air gap. The measurements were taken by fixing the hollow sphere by the aid of a screw metal stud at a distance of 0 to 25 mm with a step of 1,25 mm. Next, by measuring the voltage u and the current i and by knowing the active resistance R the flux can be calculated by solving (9):

$$\psi(t) = \int (u(t) - i(t) \cdot R) \cdot dt \quad (9)$$

The experimental setup for this measurement is shown in Fig. 7(a) and the family of flux linkage curves is shown in Fig. 7(b).

Fig. 7. Setup for measuring the flux linkage (a), and the family of flux linkage curves (b)

The bottom curve in Fig. 7(b) corresponds to the farthest distance, i.e. the one where no saturation is observed because of the minimum inductance. The top curve corresponds to the minimum air gap where the inductance is maximized. It can be seen in the figure that the bottom adjacent curves are very close to each other. That means that a small error in the flux linkage will result in a large error in the distance estimation which will reduce the accuracy. This statement covers the observations made for Fig. 2.

The measurement data can be entered into a look-up table (LUT) as shown in Fig. 8.

Fig. 8. Air gap estimation by measuring the voltage and the current

The fact is that the actual air gap value can be estimated by only measuring the voltage and the current can help in implementing a sensorless control MLS, thus fully eliminating the distance sensor. In order to make this algorithm possible, it is necessary to do preprocessing of the incoming data, expressed mostly in digital filtering in real time. That means that a faster controller may be needed. Also the look-up table is to be prepared in advance.

Future work

Although the presented laboratory model of a magnetic levitation system is complete and fully operational, there is a wide field for future work. Some of the ideas include:

- Eliminating the feedback sensor by finishing the air gap estimation algorithm, based on (9);

- Finding a suitable faster microcontroller. A possible solution is to use the much more powerful Teensy board that is based on the Arm Cortex-M CPU or even a small field programmable gate array (FPGA). A very good candidate in this regard is the Alorium Technology XLR8 board that includes a fully compatible Arduino core and a free reconfigurable fabric both embedded into a single Intel MAX 10 FPGA device;
- Adding a small display and rotary encoders for manually setting the tuning coefficients that will make the laboratory model a self-contained device;
- Extending the firmware to support direct communication with mathematical packages such as the free SciLab software. This will allow to deploy complex mathematical models in a hardware-in-the-loop (HIL) configuration.

The idea of enabling the proposed setup for remote access also exists thus ensuring that the device will be ready for distance learning. This step will require some additional mechanical components in order to prevent the ball from falling out and some firmware modifications that should provide a reliable way for restoring the system in the initial state.

Conclusions

The magnetic levitation technology makes it possible to eliminate friction and reduce wear of critical machine parts, which aids in achieving very high speeds without loss in applications such as the magnetic levitation trains and many others, which determines the increasing attention by the industry. Together with the increasing accessibility and computing capabilities of the hardware, this makes the topic relevant and mandatory for study in automatic control courses.

This paper presents a laboratory model of a single degree of freedom magnetic levitation system built at the University of Mining and Geology „St. Ivan Rilski“. The principle of operation and the mathematical description are introduced together with the feedback types, the power stage and a possible digital implementation of the control algorithm. The research is supported by a physical experiment that proves the operability of the system. A way to implement sensorless control is suggested, which is also supported by a physical experiment. The built system allows upgrading and opens a broad field for research.

Acknowledgements. The support for this work is provided by the bilateral Chinese-Bulgarian scientific project of the National Science Fund of the Ministry of Education and Science with contract No KP-06-China/2 D-83/2018 between the China University of Mining and Technology and the University of Mining and Geology “St. Ivan Rilski”, Sofia.

References

Alexandrov, R., Zabtchev, A., 2013. Electronic System for Demagnetisation in Magnetic Separation, *Journal of the TU–Sofia Plovdiv branch, Bulgaria*, Vol. 19 “Fundamental Sciences and Applications”, 1, 205–208. (in Bulgarian with English abstract)

Feedback Instruments, 2019. *Magnetic Levitation Control Experiments*, Feedback Instruments Ltd., Park Road, Crowborough, East Sussex, TN6 2QR, UK, Manual 33-942S Ed01 122006, Feedback Part No. 1160-33942S, <https://bit.ly/2ZpAh8S>

Hiroyuki, O., 2000. *Levitation Characteristics of Magnetic Bearings using Bulk Superconductors as a Field Shaping Material*, *Advances in Superconductivity XII*, Springer, Tokyo.

Hull, J., Fiske, J., Ricci, K., Ricci, M., 2007. Analysis of Levitational Systems for a Superconducting Launch Ring, *IEEE Transactions on Applied Superconductivity*, 17(2), 2117–2120, doi 10.1109/TASC.2007.898464.

Hyung, L., Kim, K., Lee, J., 2006. Review of maglev train technologies, *IEEE Transactions on Magnetics*, 42(7), 1917–1925, DOI 10.1109/TMAG.2006.875842.

Inteco, 2005. *Magnetic Levitation System (MLS) User’s Manual version 1.6 for MATLAB 6.5*, Inteco, ul. Katowicka 36, 31-351 Krakow, Poland, TIN PL6771821666, <http://www.inteco.com.pl/products/magnetic-levitation-systems/>

Lahdo, M., Ströhla, T., Kovalev, S., 2018. Research on a 6-DoF Magnetic Levitation System, 53rd International Universities Power Engineering Conference (UPEC), Glasgow, 1–5.

Manoj, L., Nithesh, J., Manjunath, T., Gowreesh, S., 2019. Power Generation using Magnetic Levitation Vertical Axis Wind Turbine, *International Journal of Engineering and Advanced Technology*, 9, (2), DOI 10.35940/ijeat.B3153.129219.

McNab I., 2003. Launch to space with an electromagnetic railgun, *IEEE Transactions on Magnetics*, 39(1), 295–304, doi 10.1109/TMAG.2002.805923.

Peng, Z., Xie, J., Gu, F., Sharmin, N., Hall, P., Fu, J., 2018. Separation of mixed waste plastics via magnetic levitation, *Waste Management*, doi 10.1016/j.wasman.2018.02.051

Pepka, G., 2013. Position and Level Sensing Using Hall-Effect Sensing Technology, AN295044, Allegro MicroSystems, LLC, 1.

Pololu, 2019. Dual VNH5019 Motor Driver Shield for Arduino (ash02a), <https://www.pololu.com/product/2502> (last access Dec. 2019).

Qiao, X., Xiaoping, T., 2020. The Stability of Magnetic Levitation Milling System Based on Modal Decoupling Control, *Hindawi Shock and Vibration*, Article ID 7839070, doi 10.1155/2020/7839070.

Quanser, 2019. *MAGLEV: Magnetic Levitation Plant*, Document No. 525 Rev. 03, Quanser Ltd. 119 Spy Court Markham, ON L3R 5H6 Canada, <https://www.quanser.com/products/magnetic-levitation/>.

Sirgado, J., 2016. Program Magnetic Levitator Arduino library, Ekobots Innovation Ltd, <http://www.ekobots.com.br/> (last access Dec. 2019).

Vuchic, R., Casello, J., 2002. An Evaluation of Maglev Technology and Its Comparison With High Speed Rail, *Transportation Quarterly* 56(2), 33–49.

Wang, Y., Logan, T., Smith, A., Hsu, P., Cohn, W., Xu, L., McMahon, R., 2016. Systematic Design of a Magnetically Levitated Brushless DC Motor for a Reversible Rotary Intra-Aortic Blood Pump. 24th Congress of the International Society for Rotary Blood Pumps, Japan, 41(10), 923–933, doi 10.1111/aor.12965.

Yaghoubi, H., 2013. The Most Important Maglev Applications, *Hindawi Publishing, Journal of Engineering*, Article ID 537986, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1155/2013/537986>.